

Integration of **Geodetic** and **imAging**
TecHniques for monitoring and
modelling the **Earth's** surface
defo**R**mations and **Seismic** risk

Deliverable 6.4

COMMUNICATION PACK

WROCLAW UNIVERSITY
OF ENVIRONMENTAL
AND LIFE SCIENCES

TECHNISCHE
UNIVERSITÄT
WIEN

SAPIENZA
UNIVERSITÀ DI ROMA

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 857612.

Work Package	6. Communication & Dissemination
Dissemination level	Public
Deliverable responsible	Communication and Dissemination Manager (CDM) – Carina Brachner (carina.brachner@geo.tuwien.ac.at)
Number of Pages	15

Authors	Sebastian Puculek, Carina Brachner		
Revision history	Date	Details	Editor
1.1	07.02.2020	Content revision	M. Ilieva (TM)
1.2	15.02.2020	Second draft	C. Brachner (CDM)
1.3	24.02.2020	Revision	W. Rohm (IDM)
1.4	24.02.2020	Revision	N. Pfeifer (WP3)
1.5	28.02.2020	Revision	R. Hanssen (WP2)
1.6	28.02.2020	Revision	M. Crespi (WP4)
1.7	29.02.2020	Quality control	G. Józków (QM)
1.8	29.02.2020	Final check	M. Ilieva (PC)

For any clarifications please contact the Project Coordinator – Maya Ilieva: maya.ilieva@upwr.edu.pl

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1 Introduction

The Communication Pack has been prepared for easier identification of digital and printed materials, related to GATHERS project. It consists colour scheme, logo, example materials, templates, etc., which will be used in different occasions, where the information or materials, related to the project implementation are presented by the GATHERS Consortium.

The usage of this Pack is not limited to the Project participants. Other parties are encouraged to use this pack, in particular the logo and the colour scheme, wherever they share information about GATHERS project.

All elements of the Communication Pack are stored in suitable editable format in the Project Management Platform in EMDesk, to which every Partner has an access.

2 Project infographics

The recognition of the project will be based on the usage of a common style of visualisation, including colours, shapes and figures.

2.1 Project colour scheme

The colour scheme (Figure 1) aims to keep the consistency of all communication and dissemination materials, in order to facilitate the team perception. The colour scheme is based on warm soil and land range as representative of Earth Sciences.

Figure 1. GATHERS colour scheme

2.2 Project logo

The Communication and Dissemination Manager developed several variants of GATHERS logo. After the several internal rounds of surveying three logos (Figure 2) were proposed for voting during the GATHERS Kick-off meeting. The first one was selected by the participants and guests of the meeting.

Figure 2. GATHERS logo variants – the first one (a) is chosen as the official logo of the project

2.3 Partners map

For ease the presentation of the Partners by the Project members, a map of the involved Partners is prepared – Figure 3.

Figure 3. GATHERS Partners map

2.4 Infographics

The main parameters of the project, namely the number of the Partners, hosting country, duration of the project and the total budget are shaped in infographic for presentational usage (Figure 4).

Figure 4. GATHERS infographic

3 Internal Communication Guide

In order to facilitate the usage of the internal communication, a short guide with information about the internal channels is created. The entire internal communication data is summarised in Figure 5, showing details about the mailing lists, the vision of the Internal Communication Guide and including a hyperlink to the document repository in EMDesk project platform.

Figure 5. Internal Communication Guide

The banner features the GATHERS logo (three overlapping triangles) and the text 'GATHERS INTERNAL COMMUNICATION GUIDE'. Below this, it lists communication tools:

- MAILING LIST:** gathers_all@list.tuwien.ac.at
- CHAT PLATFORM:** gathersworkspace.slack.com
- WORK SPACE:** <https://app.emdesk.com>

 A 'contacts' section lists:

- Project Coordinator & Technical Manager:** Maya ILIEVA (maya.ilieva@upwr.edu.pl)
- Innovation & Data Manager:** Witold ROHM (witold.rohm@upwr.edu.pl)
- Administrative & Finance Manager:** Katarzyna KOPAŃCZYK (katarzyna.kopanczyk@upwr.edu.pl)
- Communication & Dissemination Manager:** Carina BRACHNER (carina.brachner@geo.tuwien.ac.at)
- Quality Manager:** Grzegorz JÓŻKÓW (grzegorz.jozkow@upwr.edu.pl)

 Logos for WROCLAW UNIVERSITY OF ENVIRONMENTAL AND LIFE SCIENCES, TUDelft, SAPIENZA UNIVERSITÀ DI ROMA, and TU WIEN are shown at the bottom.

This Project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 857612.

4 External Communication Guide

Similar to the summarised presentation of the internal communication information, showed above, an External Communication Guide is prepared. Figure 6 shows details about the mailing lists, the vision of the External Communication Guide and includes a hyperlink to the document repository in EMDesk project platform.

Figure 6. External Communication Guide

The graphic for the External Communication Guide features the GATHERS logo (three overlapping triangles in blue, green, and yellow) and the text 'GATHERS SOCIAL MEDIA COMMUNICATION GUIDE'. Below this, it says 'Follow us on:' and lists social media handles: Twitter (@GATHERS_EU), Facebook (@gathersEU), LinkedIn (GATHERS Project), and YouTube (@GATHERS_EU). The website 'gathers.eu' is also listed. A section titled 'USE THE FOLLOWING #HASHTAGS RELATED TO THE PROJECT:' lists: #GATHERS, #GATHERS_EU, #H2020, #HORIZON2020, #TWINNING, @EU_H2020, and @REA_RESEARCH. At the bottom, logos for partner institutions are shown: Wroclaw University of Environmental and Life Sciences, TU Delft, Sapienza Università di Roma, and TU Wien (Technische Universität Wien). A footer note states: 'This Project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 857612.'

5 GATHERS brochure

A foldable 2-page brochure in A5 format is prepared, with information about the Partners, the main objectives, the time line of the events and contacts (Figure 7).

Figure 7. Brochure: up – outer cover, down – inner information

FOR MORE INFORMATION VISIT US ON

our Project Website: www.gathers.eu

Twitter: [@GATHERS_EU](https://twitter.com/GATHERS_EU)

LinkedIN: coming soon

CONTACT INFORMATION

Project Manager:

Dr. Maya ILIEVA, UPWr
 eMail: maya.ilieva@upwr.edu.pl
 phone: +48 71 320 1951

Communication & Dissemination Manager:

DI Carina BRACHNER, TU Wien
 eMail: carina.brachner@geo.tuwien.ac.at
 phone: +43 1 58801 12277

GATHERS

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COUNTRIES

4

YEARS

3

PARTNERS

4

FUNDING

800k €

WHAT IS THE PROJECT ABOUT?

GATHERS aims to integrate innovative observation techniques such as: Interferometric Synthetic Aperture Radar (**InSAR**), Light Detection and Ranging (**LiDAR**) and Global Navigation Satellite System (**GNSS**) to detect, measure and predict mining tremors and deformations. As Coordinate and Support Action GATHERS will foster development of UPWr leaders and establish strong networks with the best Universities in Europe to form competitive research applications in forthcoming EU calls.

PROJECT PARTNERS

UPWr - Project Lead
 Wrocław University of Environmental and Life Sciences (Poland) is one of the best research-oriented universities in Poland (ranked 12 nationally), working intensively across three Priority Research Area: Environmental Sciences, Food Science and Technology, Veterinary Sciences. University mission is to promote scientific excellence to achieve global sustainability goals.

WROCLAW UNIVERSITY OF ENVIRONMENTAL AND LIFE SCIENCES

TU DELFT - Project Partner
 Delft University of Technology (The Netherlands) is a public legal entity in accordance with the Higher Education and Research Act (WHW). It is the top-ranked Technical University in the Netherlands, ranked 7th in Europe. The main tasks include providing scientific education, conducting scientific research, transferring knowledge to society and promoting social responsibility.

SAPIENZA - Project Partner
 Sapienza University of Rome (Italy) is the largest university in Europe and the second in the world for number of students and the wide academic offer that includes over 250 degree programmes and 85 PhD programmes. Sapienza plans and carries out scientific investigations in almost all disciplines, achieving high-standard results both on a national and on an international level.

SAPIENZA UNIVERSITA DI ROMA

TU WIEN - Project Partner
 TU Wien (Austria) TU Wien was founded in 1815, making it the first University of Technology in today's German speaking area. It has been conducting research, teaching and learning under the motto "Technology for people" for over 200 years.

B2B TIMELINE

The timeline shows a sequence of events from Dec 2019 to Dec 2022. Key events include: 1st B2B (PL) in Dec 2019, Road Show (PL) in Mar 2020, 1st Summer School (PL) in Summer 2020, 2nd B2B (PL) in Dec 2020, 1st hackathon 1st workshop (IT) in Mar 2021, 2nd Summer School (NL) in Summer 2021, 3rd B2B (PL) in Dec 2021, 2nd hackathon 2nd workshop (AT) in Mar 2022, 3rd Summer School (IT) in Summer 2022, and 4th B2B (PL) in Dec 2022.

InSAR - we will develop improved InSAR methodology resistive to the spasticity of the of atmosphere and surface and specific characteristics of the terrain deformations in the mining areas.

LiDAR - we will work on Unmanned Aerial System LiDAR point clouds in urban areas for monitoring mining deformation and address flight dynamic trajectory and point cloud strip adjustment.

GNSS seismology - we will learn how to optimize high rate GNSS-observations processing strategies for monitoring dynamic mining induced ground motions and integrate GNSS into seismological networks.

Actions
 1 x Road Show, 3 x Summer schools, 2 x Hackathons, 3 x Workshops, 9 x Months of Master students training, 21 x Months of ESR trainings, 4 x B2B Meetings

Results
 UPWr become a leading centre of excellence in the geospatial sciences in the CEE region. Consortium equip research staff in both hard and soft skills necessary to step up to excellence in the areas of InSAR, LiDAR and GNSS seismology by the end of the project.
 UPWr create the Leading Research Working Groups, which brings research to a new stage using the reinforced scientific networks between GATHERS project partners. Consortium train new cohorts of early stage researchers capable to find a leading role in the geospatial market.

6 GATHERS webpage

The project website – www.gathers.eu – will be released in April 2020. It is the main interface towards all stakeholders interested in GATHERS, its progress, workshops, summer schools and its results. The layout of the web page is based on an easy-to-use structure (Figure 8) via WordPress and integrated in project colour scheme.

Figure 8. Screenshot of the main page of GATHERS web-site

7 Power Point presentation template

For all presentations related with the GATHERS activities, which require slide shows, Power point template has to be used (Figure 9). The template is prepared in the colour scheme of the project and contains the graphical attributes of the project – logo, Partners’ logos, EU emblem and the disclosure sentence for funding notification.

Figure 9. Power point template

1

2

8 Deliverable template

To keep consistency in preparation of the main documentation, a template for the text of all deliverables is prepared, using the style and the colour scheme of the project. The template contains the mandatory information about the name of the Deliverable, name of the Work Package to which is associated, responsible person, revision history, source of funding. Also, all mandatory graphical attributes, namely the project and Partners' logos are included. The template is presented in Annex 1 to the D6.4 Communication Pack.

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Annex 1: Deliverable template

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TecHniques for monitoring and
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Deliverable X.X

INSERT TITLE HERE

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OF ENVIRONMENTAL
AND LIFE SCIENCES

TECHNISCHE
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WIEN

SAPIENZA
UNIVERSITÀ DI ROMA

Work Package	X. Title
Dissemination level	Public or Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)
Deliverable responsible	Role – Name Surname (email)
Number of Pages	

Authors			
Revision history	Date	Details	Editor
...
...
...

For any clarifications please contact the Project Coordinator – Maya Ilieva: maya.ilieva@upwr.edu.pl

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Abbreviations

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P
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R
S
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U
V
W
X
Y
Z

1 Heading 1

Text

1.1 Heading 2

Text

1.1.1 Heading 3

Text¹

Table 1. ...

...
....

Figure 10. ...

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Figure 1. 16

List of tables

Table 1. 16

¹

